

Dynamic Management of IP Virtual Network Topology over Multi-Granular (Wavelength and Waveband) Optical Networks

R. Muñoz⁽¹⁾, V. Lohani⁽¹⁾, C. Manso⁽¹⁾, Ll. Gifre⁽¹⁾, R. Casellas⁽¹⁾, A. Sgambelluri⁽²⁾, N. Sambo⁽²⁾, M. Enrico⁽³⁾, H. Zaid⁽⁴⁾, C. Schmidt-Langhorst⁽⁴⁾, J. Vilchez⁽¹⁾, C. Schubert⁽⁴⁾, R. Freund^(4,5), R. Vilalta⁽¹⁾, R. Martínez⁽¹⁾, J.M. Fàbrega⁽¹⁾

⁽¹⁾ Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC-CERCA), Spain, raul.munoz@cttc.es

⁽²⁾ Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Italy,

⁽³⁾ HUBER+SUHNER Polatis, United Kingdom

⁽⁴⁾ Fraunhofer Institute for Telecommunications, Heinrich-Hertz-Institut, Germany

⁽⁵⁾ Technical University of Berlin, Germany

Abstract *This paper presents a multi-layer transport SDN controller architecture and resource assignment algorithm to manage dynamic IP full-mesh virtual network topologies over ultra-wideband WDM optical networks that combine wavelength and waveband switching by providing waveband channels between IP routers that are backfilled with wavelength channels. ©2024 The Author(s)*

Introduction

Total international bandwidth represents a 4-year compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 28%^[1]. Assuming a conservative CAGR of 25%, consistent with modest traffic forecasts, the projected spectrum demand by 2031 is expected to reach 50 THz^[2]. Ultra-wideband (UWB) WDM systems represent an emerging solution poised to significantly enhance the capacity of optical networks by utilizing the full optical spectrum across all available bands in standard single-mode fiber (SSMFs).

Currently, WSSs are commercially available for the C+L bands. However, as the complexity of WSSs increases with bandwidth and optical resolution, maintaining the same level of optical granularity across all bands becomes challenging. The prevailing strategy involves using band multiplexers/demultiplexers to manage each band individually and perform wavelength switching for each one. Although this approach offers the best performance, it introduces significant complexity (and consequently, cost) at the ROADMs since wavelength switching is performed within each band^[3]. The FLEX-SCALE project^[4] proposes a solution based on novel Multi-Granular optical node (MG-ON) architecture that can realize reconfigurable WaveBand-Selective Switching (WBSS), in addition to the spectral (i.e. wavelengths) switching^[5].

The design of packet-optical backbone transport networks employs a multi-layer architecture where IP core routers are integrated atop ROADMs. These routers are interconnected through a static, partially meshed optical network of ROADMs linked by single-mode fibers. This configuration supports the creation of IP virtual links, supported by optical channels routed through multiple ROADMs, to form a partially-mesh virtual network topology (VNT). In such setups, IP flows traverse numerous energy-intensive routers hop-by-hop.

A strategy considered to reduce this burden involves dynamically reconfiguring a full-mesh VNT, enabling one-hop IP connections by establishing energy-efficient optical channels directly between routers. However, this dynamic approach significantly burdens intermediate ROADMs.

In this paper, we introduce a major advancement in packet-optical network architectures through the MG-ON, which utilizes both wavelength and waveband switching. We aim to establish one-hop WDM connections between ROADMs by dynamically setting up flexible waveband channels between the source and destination and provisioning wavelength channels within these bands using only the end ROADMs. This approach boosts WDM layer efficiency by removing the need for intermediate ROADMs to switch individual wavelengths, instead using waveband switching for grouped optical channels. We validated our proposed approach by network simulations as well as a preliminary experimental realisation using newly required SDN control functionalities.

Multi-layer control and resource assignment

Fig. 1.a shows the target scenario for IP over WDM/WBDM. A MG-ON is composed of a Waveband cross-connect (WBXC) used for spectral waveband switching (i.e., Waveband Division Multiplexing- WBDM), a set of ROADMs, one for each of the supported layers (e.g., S, C, L), and an array of Transponders (TPs) covering the supported bands connected to the ROADMs with a number of wavelegnth client ports (CPs). Each pair of WBXC is connected to a pair of SSMFs. ROADMs are connected to the WBXC with a given number of waveband CPs. Finally, the IP routers with grey client transceivers are connected to the array of TPs managed as single virtual client port (VCP). The nodes without IP routers only deploys waveband switching. The multi-layer transport

Fig. 1: a) IP over multi-granular optical network scenario. b) Example of dynamic provisioning of an IP virtual link

SDN control system for dynamic IP VNT management over MG-ON (WDM/WBDM) comprises a packet SDN controller for the IP layer and an optical SDN controller for the MG-ON layer, which are managed by an E2E transport SDN orchestrator. The E2E transport SDN orchestrator is responsible for managing the overall network policies, ensuring that the transport network operates optimally and efficiently from end-to-end^[6].

The sequence diagram in Fig.1.b illustrates the dynamic provisioning of a virtual IP link within the IP VNT. Initially, the IP operator requests a new virtual link, specifying parameters like desired bandwidth (e.g., 800 Gb/s) between the VCP of two IP routers. This request is passed from the IP controller to the E2E SDN controller ("Manual virtual link creation"). Alternatively, it can be triggered directly by the IP Controller if it is autonomously monitoring and optimizing the network ("Autonomous virtual link creation"). Upon receiving the request, the E2E SDN Controller verifies policies and the status of the IP/Optical ports before requesting the Optical SDN Controller to set up a digital service connection with the specified capacity. First, the optical SDN controller provisions a waveband channel between the pair of WBXCs connected to the source and destination IP nodes if no previous waveband channel already exists. These waveband channels initially have a set spectrum width to accommodate N transponders (e.g., 1200 GHz). To this end, the Optical SDN controller computes a route with the same waveband from the source to the destination (i.e., waveband continuity constraint) in the waveband layer and, if available, configures all WBXC along the path through the MG-ON agents. Afterwards, the optical SDN controller computes the required spectrum by selecting a pair of available transponders at the source and destination ROADMs that support the provisioned waveband and meet the capacity requirements of the requested digital service. Then, the optical

SDN controller provisions the optical channel with the required spectrum (e.g. 200 GHz) within the waveband channel if enough spectrum is available (otherwise, another waveband channel could be set up, or the spectral occupancy could be increased), by only configuring the two ROADMs at each end of the waveband channel. Therefore, no intermediate wavelength switching is required. In this way, the optical SDN controller could allocate future digital service connection requests between the same pair of IP routers by selecting other available TPs and setting up new optical channels within the waveband channel. After that, the two transponders are also configured through the TP agents. Once the digital service setup is complete, the E2E SDN Controller informs the IP Controller, which activates interfaces, configures routing on the two IP Routers, updates the VNT to finalize the virtual link setup, and communicates the successful service establishment.

Performance evaluation

We have evaluated the proposed approach using Telefonica's Spanish optical backbone network (65 nodes with 135 bi-directional links and average nodal degree 3.5)^[7] and two IP backbone networks, a partially-mesh VNT (11 nodes with 16 bi-directional links and average nodal degree ~ 3), and a full-mesh VNT (11 nodes with 55 bi-directional links). Our analysis includes the dynamic generation of IP virtual link requests, which follow a Poisson arrival process with exponential holding times and uniformly distributed requests between the IP core nodes. The incoming virtual link request capacity is fixed at 800 Gbps, corresponding to a spectrum slot size of 200 GHz (1 slot). We consider the S, C, and L bands, each offering 21 slots, totaling 63 slots. We set the number of wavebands to 21, so that each waveband comprises 600 GHz bandwidth, i.e. combines 3 spectral slots. Our path computation algorithm enforces a spectrum continuity constraint and em-

Fig. 2: Performance evaluation and experimental validation

employs a first-fit spectrum assignment.

We have evaluated three scenarios: a partially-mesh VNT and full-mesh VNT over a WDM network (C-band), and a full-mesh VNT over a combined WDM/WBDM (S-C-L-bands) network. The first two serve as reference scenarios for comparison. Results show that the full-mesh (WDM) outperforms the partially-mesh (WDM) in terms of blocking probability (see Fig. 2.a) under higher loads. Additionally, the reduction in the number of IP and Optical transponders (i.e., wavelength CPs) is above 50% (see Fig. 2.b). Our proposed strategy, the full-mesh (WDM/WBDM), can almost triple the offered traffic load for a blocking probability of 1% compared to the full-mesh (WDM). It is aligned with the tripling of the spectrum when adding WBDM. The average number of IP client ports/Optical TPs in our strategy behaves as an extrapolation of the full-mesh (WDM) approach under higher loads. The average number of waveband CPs (i.e., where ROADMs are connected) remains within reasonable values. Most importantly, Fig. 2.c illustrates the average hop count, showing that the hop count for the full-mesh (WDM) and full-mesh (WDM/WBDM) at the WBDM layer behaves similarly, while in the newly proposed WDM/WBDM network with MG-ON the hop count at the WDM layer remains at one.

Experimental validation

We designed a Proof of Concept (PoC) of a multi-layer transport SDN control system (Fig. 2.d) and implemented the main functionalities required for the proposed joint dynamic management of both the IP and the optical domain over a multi-granular optical network. This system utilizes the cloud-native ETSI TeraFlowSDN (TFS) SDN controller, which relies on a microservices architecture^[8]. The Optical SDN controller for the MG-ON, developed by CNIT^[9], interfaces with MG-ON agents developed by Huber + Suhner and TP agents developed by Fraunhofer HHI. Additionally, the IP SDN

controller interfacing with two open IP routers and the E2E Transport SDN orchestrator are provided by CTTC. In this PoC, we focus on the proposed IP virtual link provisioning by joint SDN control at both, the IP and optical domains. Therefore, the agents solely serve as NETCONF configuration endpoints (without underlying data plane equipment) while the two IP routers are directly interconnected using optical client pluggables (Fig. 2.g).

Initially, the IP SDN controller requests the provisioning of a virtual 800G link between IP1 CTP1 and IP2 CTP1 to the E2E SDN controller. The E2E SDN controller then maps the client IP port to the optical ports and requests a digital service connection to the Optical SDN controller between OTP1.1 connected to MG-ON1 and OTP3.1 connected to MG-ON3. Upon receiving the request, the Optical SDN controller provisions a 300-GHz waveband channel embracing two 150-GHz media channels, inside one of them an 800G optical channel (80-GBd DP-64QAM)^[9] between OTP1.1 and OTP3.1 is created, responding back to the E2E orchestrator. Subsequently, the IP SDN controller issues a NetConf/OpenConfig request to activate the IP ports and routing tables associated with CTP1 on IP1 and IP2 and updates the VNT by adding a new link. Fig. 2.e displays the GUI of the TFS IP SDN controller, showing the IP topology before and after provisioning the new link. We then performed a ping test between the two IP routers to confirm connectivity, as illustrated in Fig. 2.f. For a second request, the IP SDN controller requests another virtual link between CTP2 of IP1 and IP2. In this instance, the Optical SDN controller only provisions the optical channel within the established waveband channel using OTP1.2 and OTP3.2.

Conclusions

This paper has demonstrated the dynamic management of full-mesh VNTs by providing waveband channels between IP routers that are backfilled with wavelength channels to deploy virtual IP links.

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References

- [1] TeleGeography. "Executive summary. telegeography ip networks research service". (2024), [Online]. Available: <https://www2.telegeography.com/hubfs/assets/product-tear-sheets/product-page-content-samples/global-internet-geography/telegeography-global-internet-geography-executive-summary.pdf> (visited on 04/24/2024).
- [2] NetworkEurope. "Strategic research and innovation agenda 2022". (2022), [Online]. Available: <https://bscw.5g-ppp.eu/pub/bscw.cgi/d516608/SRIA-2022-WP-Published.pdf> (visited on 04/24/2024).
- [3] D. Uzunidis, K. Moschopoulos, C. Papapavlou, *et al.*, "A vision of 6th generation of fixed networks (f6g): Challenges and proposed directions", vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 758–815, 2023.
- [4] I. Tomkos, D. Uzunidis, K. Moschopoulos, *et al.*, "The role of optical networking in the 6g era", in *Proceedings of Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC)*, San Diego, California, USA, 2024.
- [5] FLEX-SCALE. "D3.1: Design of multi-granular sdm/uwb optical switch node". (2023), [Online]. Available: <https://6g-flexscale.eu/en/outcomes> (visited on 04/24/2024).
- [6] R. Muñoz, V. Lohani, R. Casellas, R. Martínez, and R. Vilalta, "Control of packet over multi-granular optical networks combining wavelength, waveband and spatial switching for 6g transport", in *Proceedings of Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC)*, San Diego, California, USA, 2024.
- [7] FLEX-SCALE. "D2.1: 6g network requirements". (2023), [Online]. Available: <https://6g-flexscale.eu/en/outcomes> (visited on 04/24/2024).
- [8] R. Vilalta, R. Muñoz, R. Casellas, *et al.*, "Teraflow: Secured autonomic traffic management for a tera of sdn flows", in *Proceeding of 2021 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 377–382.
- [9] A. Sgambelluri, N. Sambo, M. Ismaeel, *et al.*, "Teraflowsdn controlling sdm and wideband optical networks", in *Proceedings of Optical Fiber Communications Conference and Exhibition (OFC)*, San Diego, California, USA, 2024.